

Classification and Mapping of PSS Evaluation Approaches

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Abstract: The evaluation of a Product-Service System (PSS), particularly during its design phase but also throughout its lifecycle, is a challenging problem. It exhibits dynamic nature and is multidimensional, since a large network of stakeholders are usually involved in the design and development of PSS eco-systems and their influence must be considered during the evaluation of the PSS offering. Nevertheless, an effective PSS evaluation can determine the market success of the PSS offering, leading to fewer design modifications and shortened time-to-market. Still, existing literature lacks an exhaustive review and classification of PSS evaluation approaches. Moreover, a lack of critical in-depth validation of performance approaches in real industrial environments is observed. Towards bridging this gap, the present work identifies the most important perspectives in the PSS ecosystem, such as supplier selection and service level, and discusses the utilised evaluation approaches used for each of them. Based on this review, a classification of existing PSS evaluation approaches is provided, by mapping these PSS eco-system perspectives to the methods most frequently used for their evaluation. The results can be used as guidelines for PSS vendors to select the most suitable method for the evaluation of their PSS offerings.

Keywords: Performance evaluation, Classification, Manufacturing systems, Systems design, Life cycles

1. INTRODUCTION

As a consequence of the manufacturing systems evolution from craftsmanship to customer-oriented manufacturing paradigm (Mourtzis & Doukas, 2014), the servitization of manufacturing and the Product-Service Systems (PSS) have been globally observed the past few years (Meier et al., 2010). PSS can be described as a hybrid solution comprising products and services for the purpose of increasing value for customers (Shimomura et al., 2015). PSS is an inherently dynamic, multi-dimensional concept (Goedkoop et al., 1999 and Lee et al., 2012), includes various actors (Xing et al., 2013), and presents uncertainties in its design (Chen et al., 2015), rendering its evaluation a challenging task. The evaluation becomes even more challenging due to the interrelated structure of stakeholders who have a long-term relationship and communication with each other (Baines et al., 2007, and Shimomura et al., 2015). Academic community has long been aware of the importance of evaluation in the PSS development stages (Komoto & Tomiyama, 2008), but as initially indicated by Baines et al. (2007), later by Vasantha et al. (2012), and more resent by (Tran & Park, 2015), the evaluation of PSS is still an immature field with few concrete results and approaches. Due to the substantial differences between products and services, the concept of PSS evaluation differs from conventional evaluation problems, since product and service activities interact and influence each other (Chen et al., 2015). Furthermore, the relationships among the criteria of the PSS concept are much more complicated than those of pure products or services (Lee et al., 2012). The previous cause the PSS solution evaluation process to be treated as a complex multi-criteria decision-making problem (Chen et al., 2015).

Considering modern requirements, such as the need to respond rapidly, accurately, and efficiently to volatile market demands, the competitiveness and sustainability of an enterprise can only be sustained by a continuous monitoring of the performance throughout the lifecycle of their PSS offerings. Similarly, concept evaluation is also vital for PSS success. Measuring the performance of PSS is one of the most important tasks for a firm since it influences its competitiveness in the market, its cost-effectiveness, and finally, its business performance. This task aims at waste elimination, better process control, efficient manpower utilization, and employment of flexible systems (Chryssolouris, 2006).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW ON PSS EVALUATION

Over the last decade, much research has been carried out on PSS design methods, methodologies, and tools, while there are numerous review papers which gather this research, however, the PSS concept evaluation is yet at a preliminary level (Baines et al., 2007, Vasantha et al., 2012, and Tran & Park, 2015). Yet, the evaluation of PSS has not been in focus of PSS researchers in early years, due to the fact that emphasis was given on development methodologies. This fact is reflected in Fig. 1, in which search results about the general PSS literature, and the corresponding about the PSS evaluation methods, from Google Scholar and Scopus citation databases, are presented. In the period between 1999-2016, only 18% of the literature related to PSS work mentions the importance of PSS evaluation, while only 5% provides comprehensive PSS evaluation approaches. Interestingly, as depicted in Fig. 1, although the formal PSS topic was introduced in 1999 by Goedkoop et al. (1999), the

first work on PSS evaluation appears 8 years later in the work of Shimomura & Sakao (2007). The investigation of the literature led to the identification of the following widely-considered PSS perspectives: customer, sustainability, early design, risk and uncertainty, knowledge, suppliers' selection, service level, human resource allocation, cost, feasibility of new PSS idea, and lifecycle.

Fig. 1. Comparison between literature on PSS (blue bar) and PSS evaluation (red bar).

2.1 Customer perspective of PSS evaluation

For realizing value in a PSS, the design should be focused on customers and their requirements. Therefore, the evaluation of customer satisfaction, in order to support the PSS design, has attracted attention in the PSS research community. Many methods have been suggested for that purpose, mainly using decision making theory. Regarding customer satisfaction, existing studies aim at designing PSSs effectively and efficiently, considering customer satisfaction for design alternatives. Kimita et al. (2008a) introduce a method for estimating customer satisfaction using a non-linear value function, which enables designers to compare design solutions at the conceptual stage. Geng & Chu (2012) evaluate the customer satisfaction in the PSS concept by using Important-Performance Analysis (IPA) integrating the Kano's model and by taking into consideration the mutual influence relationships among attributes by Decision Making Trial and Evaluation Laboratory (DEMATEL). Moreover, Pan & Nguyen (2015) used the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) and Multiple Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) approaches in order to identify appropriate performance criteria for the purpose of achieving customer satisfaction. The transition from purely product-oriented offerings to PSS is difficult since many customers hesitate to adopt this new concept. This issue is recognized by Lee et al. (2015), contributing to support PSS strategies by evaluating their likely acceptability by customers. This is carried out through combining the Analytic Network Process and the Niche Theory to quantify customer value on given PSS offerings. Regarding the evaluation of customer requirements, Song et al. (2013) suggest a framework for addressing the vagueness and the subjectivity of the evaluation of these requirements. The proposed model evaluates requirements under vagueness, considering the customer activity cycle, using Rough Group Analytic Hierarchy Process methods. In the same direction, Lee & Huang (2009) developed the fuzzy Kano's questionnaire (FKQ) and the fuzzy Kano's mode (FKM) for analysing customer requirements. After the questionnaires are completed, the designers can obtain data sets of customer expectation, quality, and satisfaction.

2.2 Sustainability perspective of PSS evaluation

PSS is the *par excellence* business strategy that promises sustainability (Goedkoop et al., 1999 and Baines et al., 2007). For a sustainable growth of a PSS, the evaluation should be done in a balanced manner, which covers the basic sustainability pillars, namely environment, economy, and society. However, the majority of literature on PSS evaluation, usually focuses on addressing the aspect of "environmental" performance of PSS, while very few are devoted to the evaluation of the tree perspectives (Peruzzini et al. 2013). Works that integrate all three aspects into the evaluation procedure are very limited (Lee et al., 2012 and Kim et al., 2013). Sustainability problems are characterized by divergent values and norms among decision-makers, high uncertainty about causes, solutions, and risks (Chen et al., 2015). For this reason, most of the literature work, addresses the problem of sustainability evaluation as a fuzzy decision-making problem. Moreover, axiomatic design provides a logical and systematic method for creating and evaluating PSS design (Kimita et al., 2008a), which is a solution based on the *hybrid* uncertain Information Axiom. The term *hybrid* characterizes the environment that is governed at the same time by fuzziness and randomness. Taking advantages of the previous concepts, Chen et al. (2015) propose an evaluation method based on the Information Axiom, in order to evaluate PSS solutions within *hybrid* environments. Hu et al. (2012) propose a PSS evaluation model based on the Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process, while Lee et al. (2012) suggest a dynamic and multidimensional approach to measure PSS sustainability, using the System Dynamics (SD) simulation method and "triple bottom line" (TBL) approach for the systematically linked socio-economic-environmental sustainability system. The index measurement approach proposed by Xing et al. (2013) comprises an approach that utilises appropriate indicators to measure performance, cost, and environmental impact. For measuring purposes, the Net Present Value (NPV) and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) are applied. Abramovici et al. (2014) propose a framework of KPIs in order to evaluate sustainability aspects through the entire PSS lifecycle. Moreover, Chirumalla et al. (2013) recommend a performance measurement framework for PSS development based on BSC using multi-criteria and multi-hierarchical levels. Chou et al. (2015) establish a hierarchical structure of multiple criteria for assessment of sustainability, and use a scale ranging from one to five to perform the PSS evaluation, inspired by the SERVQUAL/SERVPERF model.

2.3 Entire PSS Lifecycle evaluation

In literature, a commonly accepted PSS lifecycle is the one proposed by Rese et al. (2012) that comprise the planning, development, implementation, delivery and use, and closure. However, only few literature work is devoted to the evaluation of the entire PSS lifecycle. As previously shown, most of them target the assessment of PSS sustainability, such as the works of Abramovici et al. (2014), Xing, et al. (2013), and Chirumalla et al. (2013). It is observed that most PSS evaluation approaches that address the entire PSS lifecycle are based on KPIs. In this direction, Kim et al. (2013) propose an evaluation scheme in which all the phases of PSS lifecycle are taken into account, from customer and company perspectives, by using appropriate PSS lifecycle-

dependent performance criteria. A particular phase of PSS is the early design phase, which is utterly important for the subsequent success of the offering since it can determine the superiority of the final design solution. Few studies however, analyse and correlate the connection between PSS design process and solution (Shimomura et al., 2015). In order to evaluate the early phase of PSS design, Exner & Stark (2015) suggest an innovative approach named SHP4PSS that incorporates Virtual Reality tools in order to enable a realistic representation of different lifecycle phases. Moreover, the works of Kimita et al. focus on PSS assessment of early design phase, from both customer (Kimita et al., 2008a) and cost (Kimita et al., 2008b) perspectives. Finally, (Mourtzis, et al., 2015) gather the most appropriate KPIs for PSS, which are monitored in different lifecycle phases, and present a conceptual framework for effective PSS design models.

2.4 Cost evaluation in PSS.

Mannweiler et al. (2010) put forward a methodology to assess the costs arising throughout the whole lifecycle of PSS. In this methodology, a two-dimensional classification is carried out. The investigated costs are first classified into disinvestment, utilization, and investment, and secondly into physical components, non-physical components, and lifecycle characteristics. Another contribution for cost assessment of PSS comes from Kimita et al. (2008b), who propose a methodology to evaluate the services from both customer importance and the economic cost perspectives. In the context of this work, 15 functions and 17 activities of service engineering are considered. Finally, the financial cost of each function is calculated concurrently with a customer importance analysis.

2.5 Risk and Uncertainty evaluation in Supply Chain

Zeiler & Bertsche (2014) present a modelling method based on the conjoint system model and a Monte Carlo simulation procedure in order to simulate the reliability and maintenance for the risk management of PSS-related services in different stages of PSS lifecycle. Using fuzzy-based decision-making techniques (TOPSIS, DEMATEL, Delphi, and Analytical Hierarchy Process), suggest an approach for evaluating the uncertainty in networks of: (i) the supply chain (Durugbo & Wang, 2014) and (ii) the delivery phase (Wang & Durugbo, 2013)). In a similar context, Omer et al. (2014) uses multiple domain matrices and agent-based modelling in order to identify and evaluate a set of risk factors that concern the supply chain. Abramovici et al. (2013) propose a KPIs framework for the use phase of PSS, aiming at early risk monitoring. A two-step evaluation framework has been introduced (Sun et al., 2012) at a microscopic and a macroscopic level. The microscopic level is associated with the quality and cost of the part machining service networks, in a quantitative manner. The macroscopic level deals with the networks' time, stability and robustness. The evaluation result attempts to benefit the network's establishment, monitoring, and optimization.

2.6 Evaluation of other PSS aspects

Concentrating on the sustainability and quality of PSS offerings of a machine tool manufacturer, a software tool is developed based on a KPIs monitoring framework (Mert &

Aurich, 2015). The software evaluates the quality of PSS regarding the fulfilment of customer requirements. Sun et al. (2012) develop evaluation indices to measure the interrelationship between a PSS's provider and receiver. These indices regard time, quality, cost, stability, and reliability. For the evaluation of supplier selection, Geng & Liu (2015) propose a methodology that use the rough set mining approach for extracting the criteria weights according to the surveyed performance information, and after that, a set of criteria weights feeds the VIKOR approach that carries out the evaluation. Under the perspective of service evaluation, first Shimomura and Sakao (2007) use QFD (Quality Deployment Function), DEMATEL, and AHP (Analytical Hierarchy Process) to demonstrate a method for measuring the effectiveness of service, which is conducted by a provider during the design process in order to generate the largest value for all the concerned agents. Li et al. (2014) present the universal Enterprise Manufacturing Service Maturity Model (EMSMM) in order to carry out the evaluation of a company's current service development phase and level. Yoon et al. (2012) develop an evaluation framework in order to evaluate the feasibility of a new PSS development considering appropriate measurements from the provider and customer perspectives. From the provider side of PSS evaluation, authors focus on economic, technology, and political-legal feasibility, while for the customer's side, expected value intension to adoption, and referred use of service. Shimomura et al. (2013) propose a method to guide the human resource allocation in order to design higher quality PSS, using a neural network to predict customer satisfaction realised by each human resource. Schenkl et al. (2014) develop an enhanced MDM-based knowledge map as an evaluation framework of knowledge within a company in order to specify the required level of knowledge that provider needs for a specific PSS.

3. MAPPING PSS PERSPECTIVE AND METHODS

PSS has been established as a prevailing business model in most companies worldwide. However, academic literature presents gaps related to the evaluation approaches for PSS. Indicatively, there is a lack of critical and in-depth evaluation of PSS performance, while there are few methodologies that consider feedback from the entire lifecycle of a PSS. These gaps may be attributed to the lack of PSS-oriented software tools and the limited comprehensive quantitative methods that can help organizations understand the perceived value that a potential customer may hold and to evaluate the level of service that is required by the market. Finally, most evaluation methods consider only the customer satisfaction without balancing or reviewing it from a company perspective. Besides, most approaches emphasize on the environmental and social gains without considering the economic impact of the PSS. This section aims to provide a mapping of the existing PSS evaluation approaches according to "what" and "how" they evaluate different PSS perspectives. This mapping is presented in

Fig. 2, where the centre of cycle contains all the literature work devoted to the PSS Evaluation. Replying to the "what" question, each reference from the centre is linked to the PSS

perspectives (left hand side of Fig. 2) that it intends to evaluate. Moreover, the literature works are linked to the methods that have been used in order to build up the evaluation procedure. This right-hand side of the figure replies to the “how” question, used by the authors to evaluate the corresponding PSS perspectives. The acronyms of Fig. 3 are explained in Table 1. Additionally, Table 1 describes the usage of the main evaluation methods. This chart can be used as a quick reference for academics and practitioners who are interested in understanding: (i) which are the available evaluation methods for PSS, (ii) which PSS perspectives are addressed by existing evaluation methods, (iii) how often has each method been used, (iv) how often each PSS perspective has been evaluated, (v) and what methods and perspectives are preferred in international literature. Interpreting Fig. 3, the PSS perspectives that are mostly evaluated are denoted with heavy line. These perspectives are the Lifecycle, Sustainability, Risk and Uncertainty, and Customer Satisfaction. Similarly, the degree of the utilization of the several evaluation methods by authors, are coded with color and gradually heaviness of grey linked lines. As it is seen in Fig. 3, the mostly used methods are the MCDM, Questionnaires and KPIs. On the other hand, sparse lines deriving from a perspective and arriving at a method represent their limited use in literature.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This work presented an extensive literature review on PSS evaluation approaches, identified and analysed significant perspectives of PSS eco-system, and classified the tools that are commonly used to evaluate them. The identified perspectives of PSS evaluation were customer, sustainability, early design, risk and uncertainty, knowledge, supplier selection, service level, human resource allocation, cost, feasibility of new PSS idea, and lifecycle. Several different methods have been used for the evaluation of these perspectives, such as questionnaires and KPIs, while it was found that Multi-Criteria Decision Making is the preferred evaluation method. The deriving methods classification and their mapping with the PSS perspectives comprises a guide for the selection of the most appropriate method for PSS evaluation, for both academic and industrial applications. Future work will focus on the development of a comprehensive PSS evaluation methodology, incorporating feedback from the entire PSS lifecycle, KPI measurements from the customer side, production/manufacturing, shop-floor experts, and other relevant stakeholders.

Table 1. Tools used in the evaluation of PSS perspectives

Tool	Description of the usage of tool for the PSS evaluation
Questionnaire	Usually the first step of most evaluation approaches, which aims at gathering critical customer related attributes
IPA	Important-Performance Analysis (IPA) is a two-dimensional grid-based graphical representation of attribute performance and importance, for providing customer satisfaction evaluation (Martilla & James, 1977)
DEMATEL	DEcision-MAking Trial and Evaluation Laboratory (DEMATEL) is a tool for analysing the influence relationships among the PSS elements in a system and identifying causal and effect groups in the system through a causal diagram (Fontela & Gabus, 1976)
ANP	Analytic Network Process (ANP) is a generalization of the Analytical Hierarchy Process (Saaty, 1980), which is one of the most widely used Multiple-Criteria decision Making methods to better capture human psychology in decision making
Delphi Method	Tests a MCDM framework verifying the answers of respondents by repeatedly collecting answers of experts via interview or questionnaire surveys (Warfield,1976)
KPIs	Qualitative or quantitative indices of cost or benefit character, the value of which can be compared against an internal target or an external “benchmark” to give an indication of performance
Niche Theory	Tool for analysing the preferences of customers for new PSS offerings given its ability to examine the competition between two offerings via customer survey (Pianka, 1981)
Non-Linear Function	A non-linear function is used to estimate satisfaction, for better capturing of the relationship between quality and satisfaction in the customer perception of a PSS
Kano’s Model	The two-dimensional quality and evaluation model to characterize product or service attributes, which are classified into: must-be (M), one-dimensional (O), attractive (A), indifferent (I), and reverse (R) (Kano, 1984)
Balanced Scorecard (BSC)	BSC is a four-dimensional framework for effective management of operational organization’s activities. Its four dimensions are: financial, customer, internal process, and earning and growth (Kaplan & Norton, 1992)
Rough Set Theory	This Theory can enable stakeholders to express their true perception and evaluation without a priori information (Pawlak, 1998)
QFD	Quality Function Deployment (QFD) transforms the quantitative customer demands into qualitative parameters. In the PSS, it use to translate the customer requirements into the priorities of products-services (Akao, 1990)
SERVQUAL	Evaluates service quality (SERVQUAL) aspects using a 7-point linguistic scale. The global quality measure is the average of the dimensions in the terms of the customer’s perception and expectations towards the service (Parasuraman et al., 1991)
Neural Networks	Architecture to represent a number of PSS interconnected processing elements. These elements, called neurons, are organized commonly in three layers: input, hidden, and output layers
Information Axiom	Tool for selecting the best design solution among all feasible alternatives. Information Axiom approaches are classified into four categories: traditional deterministic, traditional random, fuzzy, and hybrid uncertain (Suh, 2001)
TBL framework	Triple Bottom Line (TBL) framework. Provides a comprehensive view, which depicts dynamic interaction among the three dimensions of PSS sustainability (environmental, economical, and societal) (Elkington, 1999)
SHP4PSS	Smart Hybrid Prototype (SHP) approach integrates physical prototypes, digital models, and software in Virtual Reality (VR) to enable an experiencing of PSS for an urban mobility use case (Exner & Stark, 2015)

Fig. 2. Mapping of the PSS evaluation approaches to the PSS perspectives.

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